

Translatability of Tenses from Russian to English and vice versa

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This paper aims to explain how to translate from Russian to English and vice-versa. Verbal aspects with associated tenses and their translatability between these two languages are highly debated grammatical categories. These two languages lack parallel grammatical categories as a result learner faces difficulty in translating tenses between these languages. Using available literatures, this paper attempts to illustrate translatability of tenses between existing unequal grammatical categories. This paper present conceivable translation of temporal and associated aspectual meaning in active forms of tenses; propose an illustration to find even grammatical category and its translation in syntactical form.

Keywords: Indefinite tense; continuous tense; perfect tense; perfect continuous tense; verbal aspect; perfective aspect; imperfective aspect;

Introduction: Temporal grammatical category is important category in language. Tense, mood, aspect, temporal adverbs, phrases and clauses play the important role in signifying temporal location of any event, process or state. This paper attempts to analyse translatability of tenses from Russian to English and vice-versa. This paper describes different forms of tense and its different aspectual bases of these pairs of language to introduce its translatability. Formation of different aspects of both theses languages is out of the purview of this paper.

This paper represents available research for the analysis of tenses along with aspects for the research. The paper describes affinity of tenses and aspects of both the languages and further explains dissimilarity of these grammatical categories between these languages and suggests a model for the possible translation from Russian to English to Russian to English. There is significant difference of tenses amid these languages as result learner faces grave problem in learning and translating. This research attempts to present an exclusive model with visual cognition and illustration to maximize leaning of Russian language.

This paper covers translation of temporal meaning covered in tense and interconnected aspectual form. And it suggests tools which can be used to translate the uneven grammatical categories of both the language.

Tense and Aspect: Reichenbach in 1947 claims that there are at most three points in time which are relevant to the choice of tense in any given sentence: S is for moment of speech, E is for moment of the event and R is for moment of reference. Tense locates an action, a process, or a state (when it happens i.e. an event time-E) in distinctive time with reference to speech-time (S) and reference-time (R). And aspect determines internal composition: state and temporal meaning of an action, a process, or a state.

In Russian, Y. Maslov in 2004 defines aspect in aspectology. In 1956 Russian linguist Aleksandr Peshkovskidefines aspect: "Aspect shows how an 'action', 'situation' or 'incident', etc. expressed with a verb has occurred in a time period or how it is divided into time periods" Osten Dahl in 1985 described that 'Russian, aspectual system is often taken as a paradigm for what an aspectual system should look like'. Russian language possesses two aspects imperfective and perfective aspects which seem to have high interrelationship with tenses. Imperfective aspect denotes event which occurs at or during speech, that is, present tense. Both imperfective and perfective aspects denote non-present-tense: past and future. Imperfective aspect denotes past tense and future tense. Past tense occurs prior to the moment of speech. Future tense happens with the help of verb «БЫТЬ». Perfective aspect produces past tense (before speech-time) and future tense (after speech-time). Therefore, imperfective aspect establishes present tense, past tense, and even future tense since perfective tense forms past tense and future tense.

Salaberry and Shirai in 2002 defines that tense is a deictic grammatical category which locates a situation in a time with respect to some other time that is usually moment of speech. Further in 2008 Cowan adds that tense has three 'dimensions': 'present', 'past', and 'future'. He further explains that merely present and past have the verbal inflections.

Aspect is grammatical category which displays the internal composition of the verbs. In 1967 Vendler classified four aspectual classes in English. Klein in 1994 describes that a speaker see aspect as temporal course of some event, action, process, etc. In 2008, Cowan indicates that when speaker view an action as complete; it perfective aspect. If viewed an action

as incomplete; it is imperfective aspect. If viewed as being-repeated on continuity, it is iterative or continuous; if viewed as occurring regularly, it is habitual. We can take four sentences as example of these four aspects. (a) He "reads" a book. Here "reads" means action is happening repeatedly therefore it is of habitual or indefinite or simple aspect (all time present). (b) He "is reading" a book. In this sentence verb "is reading" means action is happening continuously as a result it is of progressive aspect or continuous aspect. (c) He "has read" a book. Here verb "has read" means action is completely done, its effect is still existing. So, it is of perfect aspect. (d) He "has been reading" a book. In this sentence, verb "has been reading" means action is partly complete and partly being done that is why action is incomplete therefore is of incomplete aspect or perfect continuous aspect.

Russian has two aspects: imperfective and perfective; and three tenses: present, past, and future. Together with these two aspects and three tenses Russian has five forms of active sub-tenses. Present tense has only one form which is formed only with imperfective aspect, it is not formed with perfective aspect. Past tense has two forms which are formed with both imperfective and perfective aspects. Future tense also has two tenses which are formed again with imperfective and perfective aspect. English has totally twelve forms of sub-tenses which are formed with the help of four types of aspects in all the three tenses. Present tense has four forms of sub-tenses: present indefinite, present continuous, present perfect and present perfect continuous. Likewise, past and future tense each have four sub-tenses separately: past indefinite, past continuous, past perfect and past perfect continuous; and future indefinite, future continuous, future perfect and future perfect continuous.

Therefore, four types of tense-forms in all three times have deep interrelation with four aspects: indefinite, continuous, perfect and imperfect. Further these four aspects have some similar connotation with imperfective and perfective aspects which are there in Russian language. Indefinite and continuous fundamentally falls into imperfective aspect. All the tenses of English, together with verbal forms, use temporal adverbs, phrases, and clauses a reference-time which function as tool to find any action, event, process or state into a specific time to form particular tense. Russian Language uses imperfective form of verbs to express continuous and habitual action with the help of temporal adverbs, phrases, and clauses as tool to incorporate proper temporal value to form a tense.

Translatability: Here we can get the illustration of present, past and future tense and its temporal reference with respect to the point of speech (S) and the point of the event (E) in Russian and English.

Tense	Speech point (S), Event point (E) and Reference Point (R)	
Present		E coincides with S (E,S)
Past		E takes place before S (E-S)
Future		E takes place after S (S-E)

English aspectual forms are formed with the help of auxiliary verbs endings of the verbs. There are five verbal forms in English: root/ base form(V1) , past (V2), past participle (V3), present participle (V4) and third-person singular (V5). Auxiliary verbs and verbal forms with endings together form aspects. And in Russian aspectual forms are morphologically formed generally with the help of prefixes.

Aspect	English (Auxiliary Verb)	Aspect	Russian
Indefinite/ Simple	V1/V2/V5 (do)	Imperfective	Base form #
Progressive/ Continuous	V4 (be)		
Perfect Progressive/ continuous	V3+V4		
Perfect	V3 (have)	Perfective	Derived form*

The Simple and Progressive aspects are represented by only imperfective aspect of Russian.

* Perfective forms are formed generally with the help of prefixes; if verbs have regular form.

Aspect	English (Auxiliary Verb)	Aspect	Russian
Indefinite/ Simple	Do read	читать	Base form
Progressive/ Continuous	Be reading		
Perfect Progressive/ continuous	Have been reading		
Perfect	Have read	прочитать	Derived form*

Imperfective aspectual meaning of Russian language covers basic meaning of simple, continuous, and perfect continuous. There is no categorically present perfect verbal form with aspectual meaning in Russian language. It is believed in Russian that if anything is complete means it should occupy its space time in past hence past form of perfective aspect of Russian

language is used for present perfect. On comparing temporal and aspectual meaning; it is found that adverbs, phrases and clauses fill the of the meaning which is there in English but not there in Russian.

We get comprehensive tense form in English; when we add temporal reference point to locate the event. This reference point becomes significantly important when we translate tense from Russian to English and vice versa. This temporal reference become significant because it specifies the temporal meaning of the tense which gives opportunity to translator to translate properly.

Aspect	Temporal	English	Russian
Indefinite/ Simple	(Present all the time or habitual) 		
Progressive/ Continuous	(Continuation of action on a specific time) 	читать	Base form
Perfect Progressive/ continuous	(Continues for duration of Time) 		
Perfect	(Result/ completed action) 	прочитать	Derived form*

Different time references associate distinct meaning to the various verbal forms. Temporal adverbial which signifies repetition of event, process or state like every day, every month, every year etc is simple aspect and as a result simple tense. If temporal reference signifies a point of time whence event is happening is called continuous tense like now, right now. If adverbial means perfectivity is called perfect tense like already, by Monday etc. if adverbial adds duration means some part of the event or process has happened some parts of action is continued which perfect continuous like; since morning, for two hours etc. Verbal forms need reference point, that is, temporal adverbial to specify the tense. Therefore, due dissimilarity between tense and aspect, time reference (R) play vital role in tense specification-and-meaning. This temporal reference point hidden in adverbs, phrases, adverb clauses and temporal context

offer tense-meaning for the translation of the tense. Below we have aspectual simplified illustration and associated active tenses of English in syntactical forms.

Adverbs, phrases and other verbal clauses could be possibly used to associate Russian into English and vice versa. Next table covers those adverbs and phrase or other action which signals the temporal and aspectual meaning of the verbal forms in the syntactical forms. Hence, the temporal adverbs or temporal meaning of other clauses in Russian fill up the gap which caused by the various tense-forms of English which lack in Russian language. As a result, those temporal and aspectual meaning of in adverbs, phrase and clause could be used for proper translation. Following table provides examples of those translation.

Tense	Aspect of Tense	Form		Example
		Time/Verb form	Признаки	
Present	Simple (настоящее простое время) E coincides with S	English V1/V5+Ø	every day- каждый день, always - всегда, never - никогда, often - часто seldom - редко, sometimes - иногда, usually - обычно и т.д.	He <u>always</u> read it. We <u>often</u> go to the cinema. Он <u>всегда</u> читает это. Мы <u>часто</u> ходим в кино.
	Continuous (настоящее продолженное время) E happens at a point of time coincides with S	English V1/V5+V4	now - сейчас, at this moment - в этот момент, still - всё ещё, while - пока, в то время как. и т.д.	I am reading a letter <u>now</u> . He is going to work <u>at this moment</u> . Я читаю письмо <u>сейчас</u> . Он идёт на <u>работу</u> в этот момент.
		Russian Imperfective/HC		
	Perfect (Настоящее совершенное время) E happens before or at S Completely and effect is till S	V1/V5+V3	already- уже, yet- ещё just- только что, ever- когда-либо, lately- недавно, recently- недавно и т.д.	She <u>has already</u> read. He <u>has just</u> written an article. Она <u>уже</u> прочитал. Он <u>только что</u> написал статью.
		Perfect Continuous (настоящее совершенное длительное время) E happens for period of time and continues till S	V1/V5+V3+V4	for (в течение) и since (с тех пор, с). for an hour в течение часа. since six o'clock - с 6 часов for a long time - долгое время долгое время. и т.д.
Past	Simple (прошедшее простое время) E takes place before S	V2+Ø	yesterday- вчера, last night- вчера вечером, an hour ago- час назад, often - часто, sometimes - иногда, every day - каждый день, always - всегда, usually - обычно, seldom - редко и т.д.	I <u>read this book yesterday</u> . We <u>worked in the garden two days ago</u> . Я читал эту книгу <u>вчера</u> . Мы работали в саду <u>два дня назад</u> .
	Continuous (прошедшее продолженное время) E takes place before S At specific moment	V2+V4	at six o'clock- в 6 часов, at noon- в полдень, at that moment - в тот момент, when he came - когда он пришёл, all day yesterday - весь день вчера/ yesterday- вчера (в определённый момент в прошлом) и т.д.	I <u>was working at 6 o'clock yesterday</u> . She <u>was writing letters when he came</u> . В 6 часов я работал <u>вчера</u> . Она писала <u>письма</u> , когда он <u>пришёл</u> .
		Russian Imperfective/HC		
	Perfect (Прошедшее совершенное время)	V2+V3	by six o'clock - к шести часам, by that time- к тому времени,	He <u>had read the article by 6 o'clock yesterday</u> . She <u>had left before I came</u> .

	<p>Perfective/C</p>	by the 1 st of January – к 1 января / (<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в прошлом) и т.д.	Он прочитал статью к 6 часам вчера. Она ушла до того, как я пришёл.		
	<p>Perfect Continuous (прошедшее совершенное длительное время)</p> <p>Imperfective/HC</p>	V2+V3+V4	for (в течение) и since (с тех пор, с). (How long ... ? Как долго ... ?) (<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в прошлом) и т.д.	<p>He had been reading for an hour when she came. He had been waiting for two hours before she came.</p> <p>Он читал уже час, когда она пришла. Он ждал 2 часа, пока она пришла.</p>	
Future	<p>Simple (будущее простое время)</p> <p>Imperfective/HC</p>	Shall/will+V1+ Ø	tomorrow– завтра, next night – завтра вечером, often – часто, sometimes– иногда, every day– каждый день, always– всегда, usually– обычно, seldom– редко, soon– скоро.(<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в будущем) и т.д.	<p>I will read this book tomorrow. She will often think about him next night.</p> <p>Я буду читать эту книгу завтра. Она будет думать о нём завтра вечером.</p>	
	<p>Continuous (будущее продолженное время)</p> <p>Imperfective/HC</p>	Shall/will+V1+ V4	at six o'clock– в 6 часов, at noon– в полдень, at that moment– в тот момент, the whole evening– целый вечер, all day tomorrow– завтра весь день, while– пока .(<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в будущем) и т.д.	<p>I will be working at 6 o'clock tomorrow. He will be writing to her next week.</p> <p>Я буду работать завтра в 6 часов. Он будет писать ей на следующей неделе.</p>	
	<p>Perfect (будущее совершенное время)</p> <p>Perfective/C</p>	Shall/will+V1+ V3	already– уже, yet – ещё, before - до того как. (<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в будущем) и т.д.	<p>He will have already read the article by 6 o'clock tomorrow. She will have already left when I come.</p> <p>Он уже прочитает статью к 6 часам завтра. Она уже уйдёт, когда я приду.</p>	
	<p>Perfect Continuous (будущее совершенное длительное время)</p> <p>Imperfective/HC</p>	Shall/will+V1+ V3+V4	for (в течение) и since (с тех пор, с), (<u>МОМЕНТ</u> в будущем) и т.д.	<p>He will have been reading for an hour when she will come. He will have been reading for two hours tomorrow.</p> <p>Он будет читать уже час, когда она придёт. Он будет читать уже 2 часа завтра.</p>	

Therefore, temporal adverbs, phrases and clauses play important role by providing temporal and aspectual meaning to the action, process or state. Hence, before translation from Russian to English and vice versa we need to understand that context for proper translation of tense.

перевод с временными маркерами в качестве ориентира / translation with temporal marker as reference point											
Simple			Continuous			Perfective			Perfective Continuous		
To ask			To be asking			To have asked			To have been asking		
Present	Past	Future	Present	Past	Future	Present	Past	Future	Present	Past	Future
reads	read	Shall/ will+ read	am/is/are +reading	Was/ were+ read	Shall/ will+ be+ reading	Has/ have+ read	Had+ read	Shall/ will+ have+ read	Has/ have +been +reading	Had +been +reading	Will/ shall + have+ been+ reading
Читает	Читал	Буду читать	Читает	Читал	Буду читать	Прочита л	Прочи тал	Прочи таю / буду читать	Читаю	Читал	Буду читать
временной маркер											
каждый день, всегда, часто редко, обычно и т.д.	Вчера, час назад, неделю назад, давно, и т.д.	завтра, на следующе й неделе, и т.д.	сейчас, в этот момент, всё ещё, пока, в то время как, и т.д.	В 7 часов с 7 до 8, Другое действие	с тех пор, недавно, недавно, уже, только что, никогда и т.д.	В час Другое действие	в течение и с тех пор (For and since).				
Перевод/ translation											
Несоверш. Глагола			Несоверш. Глагола			Соверш. Глагола. (Прошед. Брeмени)			Несоверш. Глагола		

ConcuSSION: Russian and English language have uneven tense structure and aspectual forms hence proper translation of tense and associated aspect requires other temporal tools which locates time and aspectual meaning in the sentence. Temporal adverbs, phrases, and other clauses provide a temporal and aspectual meaning in both the languages. English language has structurally twelve forms of active tenses along with four aspects and three times: present, past and future but Russian language has only five active tense along with two aspects; imperfective and perfective and three times: present, past and future. Temporal and imaginable aspectual meaning in adverbs, phrases, and other clauses provide clue and link of tenses of both the languages for suitable translation. The proposed illustration of both language provides a frame structure of translation of tenses to the learners and teachers to learn and explain appropriate translation.

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